

International Journal of Advance Studies and Growth Evaluation

Proficient Teachers Recruitment Policies in Indian Higher Education

^{*1} Prof. Amol Bade and ^{*2} Prof. Madhavi Chinchwade

^{*1} School of Holistic Development MIT ADT University, Loni, Pune, Maharashtra, India.

^{*2} Department of Management, SNBP College of Arts, Commerce, Science & Management Studies, Pimpri, Maharashtra, India.

Article Info.

E-ISSN: 2583-6528

Impact Factor (SJIF): 5.231

Available online:

www.alladvancejournal.com

Received: 05/July/2023

Accepted: 18/Aug/2023

Abstract

In any educational institute the most important factor is the human resource. Its success is dependent on the quality and engagement of its faculty. There are different techniques and strategies are suggested by many educationalist are in force with little changes. In Indian higher education, various initiatives have been introduced and updates are being made as per the requirement in the past several years to systematize recruitment which is responsible for students overall development. As per the educational policy 2020, student's holistic development is the most important and so is not possible without the best competent faculty. The present study aims at to discuss the best recruitment policies which will be helpful for the success of Indian educational policy 2020.

*Corresponding Author

Prof. Amol Bade

School of Holistic Development MIT
ADT University, Loni, Pune,
Maharashtra, India.

Keywords: Human resource, new educational policy 2020, higher education

Introduction

Teachers are very important to mold the future of the students which is very important work for the development of the nation. It is the noble role that the teachers play therefore the teacher is most respected member of society.

Only the very best and most skillful & learned became teachers. Teachers are known as GURUs in India which has a deep meaning. They feel their ethical duty to pass on their knowledge, skills, and ethics optimally to students. The concept has been continuously changing by its nature. In the current situation the quality of teacher education, recruitment, deployment, service conditions, and empowerment of teachers is not as it should be, that's why the quality and self-motivation of teachers does not achieve the desired standards as per the current need. The high respect for teachers and the high status of the teaching profession must be restored so as to inspire the best to enter the teaching profession. The motivation and empowerment of teachers is required to ensure the best possible future for our children and our nation.

Scope of the Framework

It is important to have well established recruitment procedures which facilitate the selection of quality teachers. The teacher recruitment framework is a step forward in the direction of laying emphasis on teacher competencies and skills as selection criteria rather than merit alone. The focus is on beginner teacher and aims systems to recruit beginner teachers into their education system in a structured and transparent manner. This is based on the belief that concentrating on quality standards at entry level will ensure a gradual improvement in the pool of teachers in the system. The Framework has teacher competencies that outline components of teacher quality. The rationale for including teacher competencies at all levels in the framework is to ensure that the framework is in sync with

- i) The initiatives taken by the Indian Government to provide education to every child in the country and
- ii) The proposal made in the draft plan of National Education Policy 2020 for ensuring seamless transition in

education and quality education across levels of education. The Framework also outlines some guidelines for teacher recruitment processes.

Teacher Recruitment Process

In the current education system in India, the recruitment processes for teachers are not uniform across states and across educational levels. In order to create national standards and benchmarks for recruiting teachers, the government of India started the Teacher Eligibility Test (TET) National Eligibility Test (NET) State Eligibility Test (SET). Teacher's recruitment is done through UPSC, MPSC and some other standard tests. In this concern Government of India has given some of the rights of recruitment to the state government and to the concern institutes. The stated standard parameters are to be followed mandatorily by the education institutes or recruitment agencies.

Many times the institutions in the area of education do check the qualification eligibility by the other skills but fail to find out the skills/ qualities as teacher in the concerned area where the institute is located.

Steps of Recruitment Methods Generally Followed

- 1. Qualifications & Interview:** It is mandatory to the institutes to conduct the personal interviews and find the suitable candidate. The serious question arises with this method of recruitment that interview only is not sufficient to check the quality of candidate for the recruitment. Many examples you can find in the educational institutes where candidate recruited by this method proved to be inefficient.
- 2. Demonstration:** This method is utilized by the educational authorities with the first method given above. This method seems to be effective but it may be the case that the candidate may be the expert in the certain field on which he/she is giving a demo. This method gives an idea about the body language, Communication skills, Subject matter delivery, personality etc. Then again it seems that the process seems to be assessing the candidate more in skillful nature but when we check the drawbacks it seems to be little problematic to process the judgment. Some of the organizations do make some changes according to the need adding some extra or subtracting demo part.

Effective Steps of Recruitment Methods

While implementing this method of recruitment different experts at different level must be deployed so that no discrimination or analysis can be done properly. The each layer should be covering different sub-criteria's for the evaluation. Each criterion must be given certain weightage and at the end average is to be calculated.

- 1. Interview:** Interview should not be about the subject knowledge but rather it should focus on the psychological and personality based factors. Rather than subject experts, there should be the psychology and body language expert's. This is because candidate's subject matter is already checked in their formal education itself.
- 2. Demonstration:** Demo lecture must be organized on the spot on the specific topic he/she learned in the formal education. Here the in depth knowledge of the candidate, teaching methodology and students feedback on that must be considered for the candidates evaluation.
- 3. Group Discussion:** It is very much important to conduct the group discussion of the candidates for the evaluation as through this the candidate's cooperative nature,

politeness and empathy-sympathy towards the other party and even the overall nature of the candidate can be disclosed as a member of the society.

- 4. Interaction with Students & Faculty Members:** One session will be conducted unknowingly to the candidate which will be helpful to the recruitment process. This will help to understand the nature of candidate with the staff and students in formal & informal situations.
- 5. Test (On Teaching Learning Situations):** Certain Oral or Written Tests are to be conducted of the Candidate. Test like writing on board, live classroom observations, Students question and answering methods, psychological tests. Physical test of teaching strength etc.

Other Suggested Teachers Recruitment Processes

Recruitment Process for Maintaining the Quality Standards in Teaching with Current Educational Requirement

1. Conduction of the exam based on the teaching methodology and psychology of students and teachers on the national level. This will help the recruitment agency to understand the candidate's psychology, the knowledge of teaching-learning process and the most important the knowledge of student's psychology. Rather conducting the exams related to subject expertise as it has been already checked in the formal education.
2. Development of clear, transparent and uniform recruitment process across levels with the evidences to clarification.
3. Designing several layers of screening in the recruitment process with competent members using multiple methods of assessment to ensure holistic, reliable and valid assessment of a candidate.
4. Designate separate competent/ skillful committees for academic specifying clearly their roles and responsibilities for the smooth functioning of the recruitment process in educational institutes.
5. Provide continuous support in the form of mentoring, guiding and trainings of the new and old recruits in order to enhance their teaching and holistic skills by creating certain ambiance of teaching-learning.
6. Provide guarantee of wages and job security as per government norms in the private educational institutes.

Thus, relying on only established methods of recruitment only give faculty members in number. We cannot say that the established method is total failure. It has also given very qualitative staff members but in the current situation where there is a large number of colleges opening and large number of students getting out with degrees and qualifications, this kind of formula will help. To scrutinize the candidate this method will help and will give very good, active and skillful faculty members.

References

1. 'Teachers' Recruitment Framework', Azam Premji University retrieved from <https://cdn.azimpremjiuniversity.edu.in/apuc3/media/photos/Teacher-Recruitment-Framework.pdf>.
2. Education Policy 2020', 'National Ministry of Human Resource Development', Government of India, retrieved from https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/NEP_Final_English_0.pdf.
3. 'Recruiting, Selecting and Employing Teachers Pointers for policy development', Directorate for Education, Education and Training Policy Division, May, 2005.

4. Hammer PC, Hughes G, McClure C, Reeves C, Salgado D. 'Rural Teacher Recruitment and Retention Practices', Appalachia Educational Laboratory (AEL), 2005.
5. <https://www.skoolbeep.com/blog/reforms-for-teachers-and-teacher-training-in-nep-2020/#:text=According%20to%20the%20NEP%20guidelines,and%20increasing%20the%20hiring%20chances.>
6. <https://www.collpoll.com/blog/teacher-education-in-nep-2020/>
7. https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/NEP_Final_English_0.pdf
8. <https://www.sentinelassam.com/topheadlines/national-education-policy-2020-pg-teachers-a-must-from-class-vi-xii-580929>